

Application of Frequency Diverse Arrays to Synthetic Aperture Radar Imaging

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Abstract — Cross-range resolution in spotlight synthetic aperture radar (SAR) is primarily a function of the angular extent ($\Delta\theta$) over which data is collected. One proposed means for improving cross-range resolution for a given $\Delta\theta$ is the use of frequency diverse array (FDA) techniques. The goal is to exploit an *apparent* increase in $\Delta\theta$ to improve cross-range resolution while retaining benefits of shorter synthetic apertures and integration times.

1 INTRODUCTION

In spotlight mode synthetic aperture radar (SAR) range resolution δ_y is a function of waveform bandwidth B and is given by

$$\delta_y = \frac{c}{2B}, \quad (1)$$

where c is the speed of light. Cross-range resolution is a function of wavelength λ and the angular extent of the collection $\Delta\theta$ (radians) and is given by

$$\delta_x = \frac{\lambda}{2\Delta\theta}. \quad (2)$$

Cross-range resolution improves by either decreasing λ or increasing $\Delta\theta$, e.g., an n -fold decrease in λ improves δ_x by n . However, a modest improvement in δ_x , say a factor of $n = 2$, becomes impractical due to hardware limitations and increased atmospheric attenuation at higher frequencies. Alternately, $\Delta\theta$ can be increased to improve cross-range resolution. This approach requires greater collection time and increases potential image smearing due to target movement and/or uncontrolled platform motion during the collection.

An initial investigation considered the range-dependent characteristics of a frequency diverse array (FDA) in an attempt to increase the *apparent* angular extent subtended during collection. The intent was to exploit an apparent increase in $\Delta\theta$ to improve cross-range resolution while retaining benefits of shorter synthetic apertures and integration times. The recent emergence of FDA processing in array-based radar applications [1, 2, 3] motivated this preliminary investigation of combined FDA and SAR processing.

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2 FDA SAR PROCESSING

2.1 FDA Antenna Pattern

Traditional phased array beam scanning is achieved using a linear phase progression across elements operating at the same frequency. This steers a *range-independent* beam (far-field) to a particular azimuth angle θ_o and elevation angle ϕ_o . The FDA concept was first proposed in [1] as a method for achieving *range-dependent* beamforming. For range-dependent operation, each FDA channel operates at a distinct frequency which produces a pattern response of [3]

$$W(\phi_{El}, \theta_{Az}, R) = \sum_{p=0}^{P-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \Theta_x \times \Theta_z, \quad (3)$$

$$\Theta_x = e^{j2\pi n d_x \frac{F[n,p]}{c}} (\cos \phi_{El} \sin \theta_{Az} - \cos \phi_o \sin \theta_o),$$

$$\Theta_z = e^{j2\pi p d_z \frac{F[n,p]}{c}} (\sin \phi_{El} - \sin \phi_o) e^{j2\pi \frac{F[n,p]}{c}} (R - R_o),$$

where ϕ_{El} and θ_{Az} are elevation and azimuth spatial location angles, N and P are the number of horizontal and vertical channels, d_x and d_z are the horizontal and vertical element spacings. The beam is focused to (θ_o, ϕ_o, R_o) and varies as a function of range parameter R . The matrix $\mathbf{F}_{N \times P}$ contains the carrier frequencies of the NP channels.

Although an arbitrary set of frequencies can be assigned to the channels, an incremental frequency progression of Δf is used across the array elements in both the horizontal and vertical dimensions for preliminary analysis. Figure 1 shows the antenna pattern for an 9×1 linear FDA with a base frequency of 10 GHz, $\Delta f = 2$ kHz, and the beam steered to $(\theta_o, \phi_o, R_o) = (0^\circ, 0^\circ, 60 \text{ km})$. At a range of 60 km the beam is located broadside to the array. Given that the array spatial scanning angles of $\theta_o = \phi_o = 0^\circ$ were used, it is important to note that the range varying response is due solely to inter-element frequency variation.

Given a linear array with an inter-element frequency progression of Δf and array spatial scanning angles set to 0° , the analytic expression for mainbeam azimuth location, called the apparent scan angle θ' , is a function of range R and expressed as [1]

$$\theta' = \arcsin \left(\frac{2R\Delta f}{c} \right). \quad (4)$$

Figure 1: FDA Antenna Pattern using $\Delta f = 2$ kHz with $(\theta_o, \phi_o, R_o) = (0^\circ, 0^\circ, 60 \text{ km})$.

2.2 Proposed Methodology

Given the range varying illumination pattern, potential benefits may be obtained by using FDA processing in SAR applications. The geometry in Figure 2 is introduced to help illustrate this. For tra-

Figure 2: Proposed FDA SAR geometry.

ditional non-FDA processing, data is collected at each collection point u on the synthetic aperture of length L using a constant frequency phased array antenna. For each location u , the radar interrogates the scene at some aspect angle θ as measured from the synthetic aperture normal. By introducing FDA processing, it is envisioned that data will be collected using the resultant “bent beam” at each point along L . Thus, data collected at u is projected to an *apparent* collection point u_{app} located at an apparent aspect angle θ_{app} as illustrated. If inter-element frequency spacing Δf is adaptively varied at each collection point u , such that the FDA maintains its bent beam focused at scene center, the locus of apparent collection locations u_{app} forms an apparent synthetic aperture with length L_{app} . If

phase can be properly accounted for when forming L_{app} , it is surmised that the increased *apparent* angular extent $\Delta\theta_{app}$ should lead to a corresponding improvement in cross-range resolution per (2).

At each collection point, the required frequency progression to maintain the FDA mainbeam on scene center at azimuth θ_c is computed by solving (4) for Δf as follows:

$$\Delta f = \frac{c \sin(\theta_c)}{2R}. \quad (5)$$

To take advantage of the “bent beam” concept, the set of apparent collection points is computed. At each actual collection point u , the tangent line to the FDA beam at scene center is traced back to the synthetic aperture to locate u_{app} . The approach for phase compensation in this initial investigation is to introduce a phase delay to compensate for additional round-trip propagation time $2\Delta t$ between u_{app} and scene center. Time-domain correlation/backprojection is then used for image reconstruction.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Simulation

Simulated spotlight mode SAR processing was performed with the scenario presented in Figure 2 using the parameters shown in Table 1. Using (1) and (2), the parameters in Table 1 result in equal range and cross-range resolutions of $\delta_y = \delta_x = 0.38$ m. The resultant synthetic aperture length is $L = 1,609$ m. The target scene consists of five point targets: one at scene center, two at zero cross-range with ± 0.7 m of range offset, and two at zero range with ± 0.7 m of cross-range offset.

Parameter	Value
Angular Extent ($\Delta\theta$)	2.29°
Base FDA Frequency	10 GHz (X-Band)
Elements ($N \times P$)	9 × 1 Linear Array
Bandwidth (B)	400 MHz
Stand-off Range	40, 250 m
Collection Mode	Broadside

Table 1: Simulation parameters.

Figure 3 shows the results of spotlight SAR imaging using a traditional constant frequency array. This image is consistent with expected results.

With the proposed FDA SAR approach, the *apparent* synthetic aperture length was found to be $L_{app} = 3,218$ m with $\theta_{app} = 4.58^\circ$. The new theoretical cross-range resolution is then $\delta_x = 0.19$ m. Figure 4 shows results using the modified FDA SAR

Figure 3: Traditional SAR image.

Figure 4: Proposed FDA SAR image.

processing. Two resulting phenomenon are immediately observed: compression and spatial aliasing in cross-range.

3.2 Analysis

The cross-range compression effect in Figure 4 is attributed to the relative simplicity of the phase mapping/compensation algorithm when translating from the original u data on physical aperture L to u_{app} data on aperture L_{app} . Simply incorporating a phase delay to compensate for additional propagation time to scene center did not effectively account for propagation differences to other scatterers along the radar line-of-sight.

The spatial aliasing due to under-sampling can be avoided by sampling aperture L at intervals of [4]

$$\delta A = \frac{\lambda R_c}{2\Delta x},$$

where R_c is the range to scene center and Δx is the width of the scene in cross-range. The image in Figure 3 was constructed using the minimum required δA . When the same δA is used in FDA SAR processing, the set of apparent collection locations u_{app} spread over a longer aperture and result in under-sampling. Additionally, in traditional SAR imaging, the collection points are equally spaced along the synthetic aperture. This is not the case for the proposed FDA processing which uses the unequally spaced apparent collection points.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A priori calculation of the apparent FDA SAR length L_{app} and resulting synthetic aperture

sampling requirements can overcome the under-sampling issues. Overcoming the cross-range compression issue poses a more difficult challenge and remains a subject of interest for subsequent research. Fundamentally, the FDA process only changes target illumination characteristics in the scene without altering the actual propagation time to these targets. To accurately reconstruct an image using the longer L_{app} , each *virtual* range profile generated at u_{app} must match the *actual* range profile at that location. Future research will investigate more accurate methods of phase mapping for translating data from original u collection points to apparent collection points at u_{app} .

“The views expressed in this paper are those of the authors and do not reflect the official policy or position of the United States Air Force, Department of Defense, or the U.S. Government.”

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